

Paper 15**CUSTOMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING****Shwetha N S**Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.
OrcidID: 0000-0003-3645-8999; Email: shwethaprashanth93@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Social media marketing has become more famous after involvement of latest technologies in businesses. This is an unconventional online platform primarily for promoting goods and services, bringing customers together, and discovering and comprehending user demands via digital technologies and devices. One of the most well-known and successful methods for brand exposure and business growth online is business promotion [1]. The main goal of advertising a good or service is to make potential customers aware of its value. The advertising industry has seen tremendous change over the past few years as a result of globalization and the resulting changes in consumer purchasing patterns. The current study examines consumer perceptions of social media marketing strategies, as well as the many components of social media marketing and how they affect consumer behaviour toward product purchases [3]. One of the objectives of advertisers has always been to comprehend how consumers view social media advertising. Successful advertisements that effectively convey their messages to their target audiences can aid in promoting and raising awareness of the company's products. Social media advertising has become more dependent on various forms of interactive technology as a result of the rapid global growth of information technologies over the past ten years in order to market and promote their goods and services [2].

Keywords: social media marketing, customer perception, advertisement and technology.

1. INTRODUCTION:

For a large number of people, sharing on social media and being impacted by news, photographs, events, and opinions is a very natural process. The interest in the internet has grown throughout time as a result of social media studies and research. The Internet is actually investigated as a source of information regarding culture and society. Online interactions are facilitated by social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube [1]. It is a marketing business that is very affordable and enables organisations to interact directly with end users. Given the variety of options available to consumers and the influence that social media marketing has, brands and customers now play a different position in the organization's strategy since they have a financial impact. Brands influence customer choice and these customers influence other customers [6]. Repurchases are impacted by these changes in circumstances, which also has an impact on future earnings and the long-term viability of the business. One of the objectives of advertisers has always been to comprehend how consumers view social media advertising. Successful advertisements that effectively convey their messages to their target audiences can aid in promoting and raising awareness of the company's products. Social media advertising is increasingly relying on various forms of interactive technology to advertise and promote their products and services as a result of the rapid global growth of information

technologies over the past ten years [4]. Additionally, the concept of presenting current and exciting content could successfully entice customers to connect online. This potent quality can be viewed as the direction of advertising and could take on greater symbolic meaning in customers' thoughts than television advertising as a kind of marketing [11]. Therefore, following the debut or appearance of social media, each and every business began to conduct their marketing efforts on those social media platforms that people were increasingly using as a result of advancements in technology and the internet [7].

2. CONSUMER BEHAVIOR:

Consumer behaviour is the study of people, groups, or organisations and the methods they employ to choose, get, and discard goods, experiences, ideas, or experiences in order to meet needs, as well as the effects these methods have on the consumer and society. It incorporates ideas from social anthropology, psychology, sociology, and economics. It makorganizationses an effort to comprehend how consumers make decisions, both individually and collectively. In an effort to comprehend people's wants, it investigates consumer traits such as demographics and behavioural factors. Additionally, it makes an effort to evaluate the consumer's exposure to social influences from groups including family, friends, and the larger community. The client plays three separate functions in a consumer buying behaviour: user, payer, and buyer [5]. Even for industry professionals, predicting consumer behaviour is quite difficult. Internal factors including demographics, psychographics (lifestyle), personality, motivation, knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and sentiments all have an impact on it. Personal elements include economic level, personality, age, occupation, and way of life, whereas psychological factors include an individual's motivation, perception, attitude, and belief. External factors like culture, subculture, location, royalty, ethnicity, family, social class, past experience reference groups, lifestyle, and market mix factors can also have an impact on behaviour [9].

3. SOCIAL MEDIA:

It is referred to as a collection of online communication of many inputs, including websites, interactions, intercommunications, sharing of content, community-based or individual inputs, and many more among diverse users. Considering how various social media experts describe the term "social media" and how they define it on different points: It is an online medium for social communication that is backed by web technology services. It is a two-way communication medium that allows for the creation and sharing of information. Are websites such as Twitter, Facebook, social networking sites, blogs, social bookmarking, etc [12].

4. SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS:

(a) Mobile phones: Mobile devices with social networking capabilities are an effective sales channel. People were able to learn about the most recent developments, events, and discussions in social media with the use of mobile phones. Mobile phones make it possible to connect continuously to social networking sites, and businesses are taking use of this opportunity to update their products and services for clients via social networks [1]. Businesses use QR codes to make information about their websites and other services easily accessible to their clients. With the use of smart phones' capacity to read QR codes, customers may get information more quickly and easily [11].

- (b) Twitter:** Twitter permits the users to post one hundred forty characters to advertise and promote about their product or service. This message can be a text, website link, photo etc.
- (c) Facebook:** It is beneficial to post details about a product and to allow comments on the post. It makes it easier for the user to both like and share pages and posts on Facebook with other people [13]. Text, audio, video, and links to websites are all included in the information given. Facebook is created such that it can link to a twitter page.
- (d) Google+ :** Google + contains some of the features of Facebook and is associated with googleAdWords and maps. Google + includes location-based search, navigation services, location-based selling etc. Google+ helps in marketing activities [15].
- (e) LinkedIn:** It is a social networking platform that enables businesses to create profiles for networking with other businesses and professionals. Twitter and LinkedIn pages can be combined. It benefits users by giving them opportunities through lead generation. The pages resemble Facebook pages and can be used to advertise a company's goods and services [16]
- (f) YouTube:** Users are able to upload videos to YouTube. Businesses submit adverts to YouTube in order to target their clients. The commercial advertisements created by businesses can be utilised as a medium to market the products by way of advertisements and can represent the preferences and fashions of the customers. Videos from YouTube can be downloaded at any time.

5. IMPACTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA:

Social media, which is used for marketing, assists businesspeople in understanding their clients by learning about their preferences [4]. It aids numerous businesses in comprehending the various methods for carrying out various actions. Social media platforms are assisting in attracting new as well as many existing clients. It makes consumers more knowledgeable of how to use branded products and services. Social media platforms are not completely secure. Anyone can misuse the information on platforms like Facebook, where anyone can take someone else's picture and cause issues for customers. Due to the fact that some users of social media websites perceive these messages and emails as unsought commodities, many advertisements are being sent to these users [2]. The wrong kind of brand advertising might cause a lot of issues for the business. Despite the fact that client feedback is provided for free, many businesses do not receive it. Consumers are still hesitant to express their thoughts and ideas, though [7].

6. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The scope of the study is to assess the overall customer behavior, response of customers with regard to the social media marketing strategies adopted by the organizations. The factors to measure the attitude toward social media marketing are from secondary data, reactions to online advertisements, Experience using social media, Log in pattern, Time spent per Login session, frequently used websites & concern for privacy [16].

7. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY:

To examine consumer attitudes toward social media advertising. To analyze what aspects consumers consider while buying products advertised on social media. To evaluate how social media marketing affects customer behaviour. To understand the issues that consumers have with social media advertising [9]. In this part of the research, the researcher will describe the

used methodologies to conduct the research successfully. Here the researcher will focus on describing the philosophy, approach and other aspects of the methodology. This is considered among one of the most integral sections of the research studies- as this contains the research methodology which has been selected for the completion of this report. This will entail the discussion regarding the various research methodologies being used- in addition to the description of the respective research design implemented for the attainment of the results of this study. In addition, the related ethical consideration associated with the academic studies will also be discussed [18]. The sources of data used in this project report are both primary and secondary data. Primary data consists of information gathered from a sample size of 30 respondents residing in Mangalore, India. Secondary data consists of information that already exists and that was collected in the past for some other purposes.

8. ANALYSIS OVER SECONDARY DATA:

Regarding the enjoyment, annoyance, formativeness, believability, and demographic perceptions of consumers toward advertisements. Interactivity is thought by researchers to be another element that influences customers' impressions. Designers and marketers can more effectively strategize their online advertising designs by understanding consumers' attitudes regarding online advertising [5]. The efficiency of interactive media, like the Internet, can be increased with a greater understanding of interactivity. It is suggested a methodology for examining the elements that influence customers' impressions of advertisements, and the ramifications for internet-based e-commerce and online advertising are examined. In this study, we analyse how consumers perceive various ad kinds from their point of view as consumers. Their goal is to comprehend the perceived distinctions between traditional and internet-based online advertising for both emerging brands [11]. Ho, et. al. (2004) studied - The current study examines consumer perceptions of mobile online advertising and the link between perception and behaviour. The development of a tool for gauging opinions regarding mobile online advertising. According to survey findings, (1) consumers generally have negative opinions toward mobile online advertising unless they have specifically given their approval, and (2) there is a direct correlation between consumer sentiments and consumer behaviour. Since the respondents had negative sentiments about receiving mobile commercials, as shown by the empirical data, it is not a smart idea to send SMS adverts to potential clients without their prior consent. Given the private and intimate character of mobile phones, this may have been due to their dislike of mobile ads. They had positive attitudes, and with their consent, advertisements were issued. This implies that permission-based online advertising may become a major mechanism in the mobile environment in the future." [3]. Lertdejdech, et. al. (2009) studied - The demographics, advertising relevancy, brand familiarity, and attitude toward SMS and MMS all have a big impact on how customers react to business SMS and MMS. The data was gathered from customers in various demographic categories using questionnaires. Multiple regressions (SPSS 16.0) were used to determine whether consumer attitudes toward SMS and MMS had a significant impact on how they responded to advertisements. On the basis of the statistical research, we offer broad recommendations for an efficient SMS/MMS marketing strategy. Users of Chi (2011) believe Online advertising varies based on the social network, which implies that customer responses to social media marketing may be greatly influenced by user motives for online social networking [12]. In 2011, Phan carried out research on how social media affects consumers' views and buying inclinations. The author posited that people who are well

conversant with the latest communication technologies have contributed to the popularity of social media as it is consumer-friendly and instinctive. However, the author believes that purchase intentions and perceptions of consumers cannot be increased by investments in social media as it is in its initial Phase and has to go a long way head. According to research by Ateş Bayazıt Hayta (2013), social media is one of the most crucial platforms for communication. Social media has a significant impact on how consumers acquire information about the products and services they should buy based on their needs [5]. Additionally, researchers looked into how social media, which has recently changed how we live and added a new dimension to the Internet, influences consumer purchasing behaviour.

9. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:

The majority of consumers find it convenient to have many options from which to choose the best product. Consumer pricing comparison is made simple. Consumer time savings to locate the best items. It is suggested that marketers create a system to identify false information and to offer insightful product and service-related information. Given that most users of social media ignore advertisements, Marketers might make an effort to improve the appeal of these commercials. When promoting their products or services online, advertisers and marketers via social media, merchandise.

10. CONCLUSION:

Social media marketing is connecting with your audience using social media platforms in order to develop your brand, boost sales, and enhance website traffic. In order to do this, you need to provide compelling material to your social media sites, interact with your followers, analyse your data, and execute social media ads [13]. India is quickly becoming one of the few nations in the world with social network growth that is faster than the average for the entire world. Further study on various product and service categories, as well as research to enhance and popularise current strategies, can be performed by marketers to effectively position their goods and services in the minds of consumers [5].

REFERENCE:

- [1] Motwani, D., Shrimali, D., & Agarwal, K. (2014). Customer's attitude towards social media marketing. *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research (JBM&SSR)*, 3(4).
- [2] Yadav, M., & Rahman, Z. (2017). Measuring consumer perception of social media marketing activities in e-commerce industry: Scale development & validation. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 1294-1307.
- [3] Padival, A., Michael, L. K., & Hebbar, S. (2019). Consumer perception towards social media advertisements: A study done in a semi-urban city of South India. *Indian Journal of Marketing*, 49(2), 38-51.
- [4] Akar, E., & Topçu, B. (2011). An examination of the factors influencing consumers' attitudes toward social media marketing. *Journal of internet commerce*, 10(1), 35-67.
- [5] Shareef, M. A., Mukerji, B., Dwivedi, Y. K., Rana, N. P., & Islam, R. (2019). Social media marketing: Comparative effect of advertisement sources. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 46, 58-69.
- [6] Alalwan, A. A. (2018). Investigating the impact of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention. *International Journal of Information Management*, 42, 65-77.

- [7] Schivinski, B., & Dabrowski, D. (2016). The effect of social media communication on consumer perceptions of brands. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 22(2), 189-214.
- [8] Ceyhan, A. (2019). The impact of perception related social media marketing applications on consumers' brand loyalty and purchase intention. *EMAJ: Emerging Markets Journal*, 9(1), 88-100.
- [9] Alalwan, A. A., Rana, N. P., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Algharabat, R. (2017). Social media in marketing: A review and analysis of the existing literature. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 1177-1190.
- [10] Boateng, H., & Okoe, A. F. (2015). Determinants of consumers' attitude towards social media advertising. *Journal of Creative Communications*, 10(3), 248-258.
- [11] Ariffin, S. K., Ihsannuddin, N. Q., & Mohsin, A. M. A. (2021). The influence of attitude functions on Muslim consumer attitude towards social media advertising: a case of bubble tea. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, (ahead-of-print).
- [12] Chu, S. C., Kamal, S., & Kim, Y. (2013). Understanding consumers' responses toward social media advertising and purchase intention toward luxury products. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 4(3), 158-174.
- [13] Dwivedi, Y. K., Kapoor, K. K., & Chen, H. (2015). Social media marketing and advertising. *The Marketing Review*, 15(3), 289-309.
- [14] Daroch, B. (2017). Consumer's perception towards social media advertising. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies*, ISSN: 2455-2992, 2(2).
- [15] Radi, S. A., & Shokouhyar, S. (2021). Toward consumer perception of cellphones sustainability: A social media analytics. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 25, 217-233.
- [16] Vinerean, S., Cetina, I., Dumitrescu, L., & Tichindelean, M. (2013). The effects of social media marketing on online consumer behavior. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(14), 66.
- [17] Arora, T., & Agarwal, B. (2019). Empirical study on perceived value and attitude of millennials towards social media advertising: a structural equation modelling approach. *Vision*, 23(1), 56-69.
- [18] Wibowo, A., Chen, S. C., Wiangin, U., Ma, Y., & Ruangkanjanases, A. (2020). Customer behavior as an outcome of social media marketing: The role of social media marketing activity and customer experience. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 189.